

Obedience Attitude in *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized*. Learning Indonesian Language with Character Value

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Abstract

This study aims to describe the representation of obedience attitudes in the novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized* by Marah Rusli and its relevance to character education in elementary schools. The research data are words and statements from the novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized* by Marah Rusli. Data collection techniques are carried out through literature studies and documentation followed by reading and note-taking techniques. Data analysis uses content analysis using a literary sociology approach and data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawn. The validity of the data used is data triangulation, namely by comparing the results of observations, interviews, and documentation to ensure consistency and credibility of the data. The results of the study show that the novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized* depicts an attitude of obedience that can be used as an example for students in understanding the importance of respecting parents, teachers, and social norms. The obedience attitude shown in the characters of this novel is relevant to the value of character education in elementary school, which focuses on the formation of discipline, responsibility, and respect for social values. These findings imply that literary works, such as *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized*, can be used as an effective learning tool in introducing and strengthening character values in the elementary school environment.

Keywords: *obedience attitude, Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized, Sitti Nurbaya: Kasih Tak Sampai, literary sociology, learning, Indonesian literary.*

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Introduction

The reform era demands the formation of a complete and synergistic character education. Education that strengthens character values based on the principles in Pancasila is believed to be able to bring progress in the civilization of the Indonesian nation. Character education in Indonesia is increasingly receiving serious attention from various circles. The attention shown by the Minister of National Education is about strengthening early literacy as part of realizing the ideals of the Indonesian nation through education (Fitrianingtyas et al., 2023). In the midst of rapid technological and information developments, the challenges in shaping the character of the younger generation are becoming increasingly complex. One of them is through literary works created by someone who has valuable value judging from the content of their content (Alanur et al., 2023). Every novel produced by well-known authors in Indonesia makes an ideal contribution to students who are undergoing education as a means of developing all their potential. (Moto, 2019). This situation makes it easy for teachers to strengthen the character of their students through the content of the story played by the characters in the novel (Syarah Ihsani, 2023). Novels as one of the literary media can play an important role in character education, especially at the elementary school level (Hastuti, 2018). In this context, the novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized* (*Sitti Nurbaya: Kasih Tak Sampai* in Indonesian) by Marah Rusli has moral values that can be used as teaching materials in learning Indonesian. This research focuses on exploring students' obedience attitudes through learning the novel and its relevance to character education in elementary schools.

The role of literary works that can contribute to readers related to character values is studied with a literary sociology approach (Widayati, 2023). Literary works are studied sociologically, emphasizing how literary works can influence readers through the social roles carried out between characters. Social values that reflect the existence of positive characters that are relevant to education in elementary schools are the main elements discussed in this study. The novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized* has content that depicts the ethics of women who obey their husbands. The values of education that have been contained are religiosity, tolerance, respect for others, honesty, and responsibility (Saddhono et al., 2017). However, it was found that the underlying problem of the implementation of this research is that there is no representation of obedience attitudes produced through the role of inter-characters as a reinforcement of character education in elementary schools (Ismawati, 2018; Wiryadiningsih et al., 2020). Therefore, learning Indonesian using teaching materials in the form of literary works in the form of novels is expected to be able to explore the attitude of obedience which is included in moral values. The description of moral values represented by obedience attitudes and resulting from efforts to connect social values is expected to have relevance to the elements of character education in elementary schools.

The main problem in this study is how to explore the representation of obedience attitudes in the novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized* in Indonesian learning in elementary schools. It is hoped that the attitude of obedience produced through the role of inter-figures can provide understanding to students to always reflect obedient and obedient behavior to the rules of order in schools which aims to form a superior generation and have character in accordance with the values of Pancasila. Character education values that are relevant to obedience include, honesty, responsibility, discipline, obedience, empathy, cooperation, respect, independence, and social concern (Lestari & Rahmat, 2022; Widayati et al., 2023). The element of character education can be explored from literary works in the form of novels as a medium and

source of learning in Indonesian in elementary schools. The urgency of the research is shown through the author's concern in integrating the attitude of obedience in each character that is told in an interesting way so that students are interested in learning Indonesian in order to strengthen character education. The use of novels as a medium and learning resource in learning Indonesian in elementary schools is expected to be able to provide an understanding by deeply interpreting how positive character is realized, one of which is by being obedient to parents, teachers, and every individual who is a human being who must be respected (Nilawijaya & Anggraini, 2021). Thus, the expected implication of the implementation of this research is the formation of student character that is in line with the values of Pancasila and is realized continuously through the representation of obedience in the novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized* which is evidenced by the increasingly developing language skills.

Materials and Methods

The research method used is qualitative descriptive related to the existence of literary works. This study aims to describe the representation of obedience attitudes in the novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized* by Marah Rusli and its relevance to character education in elementary schools. This study uses a qualitative approach with a descriptive method, which focuses on analyzing the content of novels through a literary sociology approach to understand how obedience attitudes are displayed in these literary works and their implications in learning Indonesian in elementary schools.

The data used in this study is in the form of the text of the novel *Kasih Tak Sampai*, which is analyzed to find representations of obedience attitudes contained in the story. The main source of data is the novel text itself, while additional data is obtained from interviews with Indonesian teachers in elementary schools related to the application of character education values in learning. The research sample consisted of the text of the novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized* and the participation of teachers involved in character education in elementary schools. Data collection was carried out through literature study techniques by reading and analyzing novel texts in depth and interviews with teachers related to Indonesian language learning. The research instruments used are interview guidelines that focus on teachers' understanding of the application of character values, as well as text analysis guidelines to identify obedience attitudes in novels.

The validity of the data was obtained through source triangulation, which compared the results of the text analysis with teacher interviews to ensure the consistency and accuracy of the research findings. To ensure the reliability of the data, the researcher also conducts member checking by asking for confirmation from the teacher regarding the interpretation of the data produced. Furthermore, data analysis was carried out using a literary sociology approach through dialectical techniques, which involved understanding the relationship between the text and the social context that surrounds it. In this process, the data will be reduced by filtering relevant information related to compliance attitudes and character education. The presentation of data was carried out in the form of a narrative describing the main findings related to the representation of obedience attitudes in the novel, and finally verification was carried out to draw conclusions about the relevance of these values in learning in elementary schools. The final results of this study provide an in-depth understanding of how the novel *Sitti*

Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized can be an effective learning tool to strengthen character education in elementary schools.

Result

Representation of Obedience Attitudes in the novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized* on Indonesian Learning in Elementary Schools

Apart from being a reading material, literature also plays a role as one of the characters building media at the elementary school level. The moral value that can be exemplified from this novel is an attitude of obedience that is relevant to social life. Forms of obedience that can be developed from the novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized* are: obedience to parents; compliance with the rules; obedience to fate; and adherence to the common interest. The issue of unity in the novel depicts individual characters. By exploring the value of obedience in the novel, elementary school students will learn to be responsible, respect parents and teachers, and respect the rules in the school or community environment. The activity of connecting the content of messages or attitude values with socio-cultural context is one way to appreciate literature using a critical way of thinking. In this case, compliance will form a good attitude, in accordance with the purpose of the Independent Learning curriculum, namely character education. Data representing compliance attitudes in novels, presented in table 1.

Table 1. Representation of Obedience Attitudes in the novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized* on Indonesian Learning in Elementary Schools

It	Data	Category	The Relevance of Learning in Elementary School
1	<i>Parents' trust is an obligation that I have to carry out even though it is difficult to accept</i>	Parental compliance	Teaching the importance of respecting and carrying out parental responsibilities
2	<i>I could not resist the destiny that had been outlined for me, even though my heart challenged it</i>	Compliance with destiny	Helps to understand and accept reality wisely
3	<i>Even though my heart was full of doubts, I still had to obey the rules</i>	Compliance with rules	Instilling the importance of obeying regulations in schools and communities
4	<i>I respect your advice, even if I don't fully understand what you mean</i>	Adherence to advice	Encourage listening to and respecting the advice of parents, teachers, or more experienced money people
5	<i>This decision was taken for the good, and I must obey for the common good</i>	Compliance for the common good	Teaching the importance of accepting decisions for the common good

Based on the table above, data 1 illustrates a child's attitude of obedience to parental commands and expectations, even though it is contrary to his own wishes. In the context of learning Indonesian in elementary schools, this value of compliance can be taught through reflective reading and writing activities. Teachers can use these data citations as teaching materials to understand the meaning of Amanah and the responsibilities given by parents in daily life. After understanding the content of the quote, students can be asked to write reflections on their experiences in carrying out the mandate or responsibility that their parents have given them. For example, writing

down experiences of helping with homework, caring for younger siblings, or carrying out parental orders even if they go against their own wishes. In addition, this data can be associated with inspirational texts or folklore that emphasize the importance of filial piety to parents, such as the story of Malin Kundang or the Crying stone. Thus, students not only understand the importance of parental obedience from the academic aspect, but also internalize the moral values contained in the text. With this learning, it can strengthen the character of students to be more respectful of parents as part of character education at school.

Then, data 2 shows an attitude of accepting circumstances that cannot be changed, even if they are contrary to personal desires. In the context of learning Indonesian in elementary schools, the value of obedience to destiny can be used to develop reflective narrative writing skills. Teachers may ask students to write down personal experiences when they encounter situations that do not meet expectations, such as not being selected for a competition, or receiving unsatisfactory test results. Through this assignment, students are invited to reflect on how they face reality and take lessons from the experience. Group discussions with trigger questions can also be present in learning, such as *"How do I accept something that goes against our desires?"*. From this discussion, students can share experiences and find various positive ways to face destiny. In addition, teachers can use this data in learning reading comprehension by asking students to explain the meaning of the quoted sentence. Through this approach, students not only learn to understand the text, but also develop a wise attitude in accepting the reality of life more positively.

Data 3 reflects an individual who still obeys the rules despite having conflicting feelings. This attitude reflects compliance with the norms that have been established to maintain order in social life. In learning Indonesian in elementary schools, this data can be used to teach the importance of compliance with regulations in the school environment. To implement this data in learning, it can be done with group discussion activities. Students are given the opportunity to discuss various rules that apply in school, then each group can represent the results of the discussion and explain why the rules are important to obey. In addition, students may be asked to write about their experiences in obeying rules that initially felt difficult, but ultimately provided benefits for them and the surrounding environment. Meanwhile, data 4 describes the attitude of a person who obeys advice from more experienced people, even though he does not fully understand the reason behind the advice. This attitude often occurs in daily life, especially in the family and school environment. In the context of learning Indonesian in elementary schools, the value of adherence to advice can be taught through reading literary texts and discussing. Narrative texts that contain dialogues between characters can provide advice and moral messages. Students can understand the advice given and the attitude of the character who receives the advice. Speaking activities can also be used to strengthen students' understanding of the importance of appreciating advice. Students can gain various experiences by telling about the advice they receive from parents, teachers, or peers. With this learning, you can not only develop language skills, but also learn to appreciate the experiences and wisdom of others.

Next, data 5 shows the importance of respecting decisions made for the common good, even though those decisions may not be in accordance with personal wishes. In daily life, situations like this often occur both in the school environment and in the community. In learning Indonesian in elementary schools, the value of adherence to joint decisions can be taught through group discussion activities and writing

reflections. Each student may be asked to express an opinion regarding class rules, but the decision taken must be mutually agreed. After the decision is made, students are invited to reflect on how they feel when they have to accept a decision that may differ from their personal wishes. Through this learning, students can develop skills to form ideas together and accept joint decisions because it is part of the attitude of responsibility and maturity in social life.

The results of this study illustrate how the representation of obedience attitudes in the novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized* can be used as a teaching material in Indonesian learning in elementary schools. The novel depicts characters who show an attitude of obedience to the social and moral rules that exist in society, which is reflected through their actions and thoughts in dealing with conflict. This attitude of obedience, both in relationships between individuals and towards applicable norms, can be integrated in Indonesian learning as a real example for students. Through this learning, students are not only invited to understand the structure and elements in literary texts, but are also given the opportunity to delve into the moral values, such as obedience, contained in the story. This approach helps students to relate literary learning to relevant life values, thereby enriching their understanding of obedience attitudes and their application in daily life.

The Value of Character Education in the Novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized*

The novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized* shows a social reality that is inseparable from the value of obedience that applies in society. The obedience depicted in this novel is not only seen in the relationship of individuals to the rules or norms that exist in the family, but also reflected in the condition of society which often involves individuals to obey rules beyond their wishes. The value of compliance in the context of Education is also relevant to the existing Character Education system in Indonesia. Of the 18 values of Character Education, five of them are relevant to the narrative of the story in this novel, namely: responsibility, honesty, social care, tolerance, and religiosity.

Figure 1. The Value of Character Education in the Novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized*

However, the form of obedience depicted in the story also shows the social reality that is still happening. An individual often has to follow the norms of society that have been passed down from generation to generation, even though it can harm himself. This event can be used as a reflection material for students to better understand that obedience should be based on awareness, not solely because of coercion or fate. Through this novel, it can be a learning material for students in elementary schools. Students can not only understand the concept of obedience, but also have implications for community life that can affect individual behavior. This will be visualized on Figure 1.

The results of this study show that the attitude of obedience contained in the novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized* by Marah Rusli is very relevant to the value of character education applied in elementary schools. This novel depicts characters who show an obedient attitude towards parents, teachers, and applicable social norms, which can be used as an example in the formation of students' characters. The obedience attitude shown in the story serves as a tool to teach students the importance of respecting rules, the values of honesty, and responsibility in everyday life. Figure 1 shows that the novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized* is relevant to five of the 18 basic values of character education, namely honesty, social concern, tolerance, religious, and responsibility. Honesty is the most important value of Character Education because it can teach students to always say and act in accordance with reality. In this novel, the main character Sitti Nurbaya shows honest behavior regarding her feelings for Samsulbahri. Although she was forced to marry Datuk Meringgih in order to save his father from the financial burden, he was honest with himself that his love only fell to Samsulbahri. Not only that, her honesty makes him accept fate firmly and more sincerely to live his destiny. In character education, honesty will teach students not to hide the truth and be responsible for their actions. Teaching honesty to children will shape the soul and character, because honesty can lead an individual to become a reliable person. Furthermore, the value of social care can be a reflection for students to have empathy and foster awareness of the surrounding environment. In the novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized* this value can be seen when Sitti Nurbaya is willing to sacrifice for her father. She accepted her marriage to Datuk Meringgih not of her own accord, but because of her love and concern for her father who was in trouble. This can be implemented to teach empathy in the school environment. Students are taught to care for friends affected by disasters, help those in distress, and respect the feelings of others. By understanding these values, every student will grow into a person who is sensitive to his environment. These simple events can make a big difference in a person's life, both from a family perspective and in the community's insights.

Next is related to the value of tolerance, in Character Education, tolerance means accepting cultural differences and customs in social life. In this case, the novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized* shows the existence of individual relationships and cultural and customary controversies. When Sitti Nurbaya and Samsulbahri show that they love each other, their relationship is hindered by social norms that emphasize arranged marriage as a customary obligation. This can describe the individual's inability to cope with social pressures, which often leads to suffering. In the context of education, these events can be a lesson for students to still respect themselves while respecting others. In the novel, mutual respect is considered a way to peace, avoid conflicts so that it can create harmony in social life. In addition, there are religious values that represent characters related to the morals of an individual who believes in the existence of God, carries out worship, and applies religious teachings in daily life. In the novel, the spiritual element is an important element because it can affect the attitude of the

characters in undergoing and responding to a number of trials. There are figures who always adhere to religious teachings in facing trials, there are also those who use life experiences as a subject for reflection so that they can delve deeper into the spiritual concepts they adhere. In the context of Education in Elementary School, religious values are important in shaping the character of discipline, honesty, and caring for others. Through religious learning that is implemented in daily activities at school, it can help students to understand and deepen religious attitudes that can be used as a guide in behavior and action. Then, the value of responsibility in character education reflects the way individuals carry out their duties and obligations with full awareness. This value can be seen in the novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized* when Sitti Nurbaya married Datuk Maringgih to save her father from adversity. She understands that the decision will destroy her and destroy her dreams, but she decides to stay married considering that it is her family's responsibility to fulfill. This value of responsibility can be taught to students through various activities at school, such as obeying the rules and bearing the consequences of their actions. This novel can give the impression that responsibility needs to be done with sincerity.

Representation of Obedience Attitude in the Novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized* as a Reflection of Social Reality

Literature often reflects social realities in society. the novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized* is one of the works that reflects the dynamics of adherence to social life. Apparent obedience in this novel is part of a diverse social system. Through the stories of the characters, this paper can show that obedience can be a source of conflict and a source of harmony in people's lives. In the context of social reality, the attitude of obedience contained in this novel can be analyzed from three aspects, namely: obedience in responding to socio-cultural norms; compliance in family relationships; and adherence to traditional systems. These three aspects can prove that rules and values that have been passed down from generation to generation can create a person's mindset. This will be visualized on Figure 2.

Figure 2. Attitude of Compliance in Social Reality in the Novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized*

Based on the image, it depicts the situation that occurred in the novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized*. Socio-cultural norms can be a pressure for an individual, because they are carried out by prioritizing family honor and referring to applicable customs. The condition of society in the novel shows that a marriage can be established not only

concerned with love, but also with the issue of social and economic status. Compliance with these norms can be seen when Sitti Nurbaya was forced to marry Datuk Maringgih in order to save her father from debt. Although she loves Samsulbahri, she has to be forced to submit to the rules set by her parents. This norm is a tool of social control that limits the freedom of individuals, especially women. Sitti Nurbaya became a victim of a policy that prioritized family honor over her own interests and happiness, thus making her suffer throughout her life.

In line with this, there is an aspect of family relationships shown in this novel. This element shows that the attitude of obedience to parents can sometimes be a dilemma for their children. It is told by a Sitti Nurbaya who had a devoted attitude towards her father, Baginda Sulaiman, to the point of being willing to marry Datuk Maringgih to save her family from economic ruin. Social pressure and economic conditions make Sitti Nurbaya indecisive and has no other choice. She obeyed his father's decision, even though her heart was broken. This event reflects the view of the rural community, obedience to parents is a burden that must be accepted. A child, especially a woman, is required to submit to the will of the parents to maintain the honor of the family even if it has to sacrifice their own happiness. Then, in the novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized*, an attitude of obedience to the traditional system was found. A woman does not have the freedom to determine her own destiny, as evidenced by the presence of Datuk Maringgih, who uses her wealth to control Sitti Nurbaya's existence. She became a victim of the oppressive feudal system. Samsulbahri, who tried to oppose this system by becoming an educated man, also finally failed to change the situation. The traditional system in this novel is described as a rule that is difficult to resist. The community prioritizes power and wealth over individual rights. Through this story, Marah Rusli criticizes the customary system that curbs freedom, especially for women who are trapped in unfair social conditions.

Discussion

The results of this study show that the representation of obedience attitudes in the novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized* is very relevant to be applied in Indonesian learning in elementary schools, especially in learning that aims to strengthen students' character. One of the quotes in the novel describes the main character's obedience to the obligations given by her parents even though it is against her wishes: "The parents' mandate is an obligation that I have to carry out even though it's hard to accept" (Rusli, 1922). Previous research has also shown that teaching obedience values can strengthen students' character and improve their understanding of social responsibility (Pratiwi, Veronika Unun et al., 2024). The implication of these findings is that through learning that integrates literary texts, students can more easily understand moral values and character, such as obedience, which are essential for their lives (Nugrahani & Al-Ma'ruf, 2024). However, this finding also has limitations, because previous research focused more on text analysis without examining in depth the application of these values in the context of learning in elementary schools (Al-Ma'ruf, 2024). Therefore, further research is needed to see how the application of character values from literary texts like this can be further adapted in the curriculum and teaching methodology in the classroom.

The results of this study illustrate that the representation of obedience attitudes in the novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized* can be used as a teaching material in learning Indonesian in elementary schools. This is in line with the findings of previous research

which shows that literature can be an effective means of teaching character values to students (Pratiwi, et al., 2024). The novel features characters who practice adherence to social and moral rules, which is reflected in their actions and thoughts in the face of conflict. This attitude is in line with the concept of character education which involves strengthening social and moral values through literary media (Agustin et al., 2024). The implication of these findings is that the teaching of obedience values through literature can make a significant contribution to the formation of students' character, especially in the context of basic education, by encouraging students to internalize the moral values that exist in society. However, the limitation of these findings lies in the lack of more in-depth research on how the direct implementation of the novel in the curriculum can be carried out practically in the classroom, as found in previous studies that focused more on the theory of literary value without paying attention to its application (Rahman, 2021). Therefore, further research is needed to develop a more structured practical approach to using literary novels as a teaching tool in elementary schools.

The application of obedience attitudes in the novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized* supports character education learning that can strengthen students' positive mindsets and attitudes in interacting in the school environment and society. This is relevant to the findings of previous research which showed that character education through literary media, such as novels, has great potential in shaping students' moral and social attitudes (Widayati, 2024). This novel provides a real example of the importance of obedience to social and educational values that can be used as an example by students, thus strengthening their positive attitude in daily life (Purwawijaya et al., 2024). The contributing implication of these findings is that character learning through literature can increase students' social awareness and discipline, which is urgently needed to form good behavior in social interactions (Al-Ma'ruf, 2017). However, the limitation of this study is that it focuses on only one novel, so generalizations to different types of literature may require further research with a more diverse approach (Hidayati et al., 2024).

Conclusion

The conclusion of this study shows that the analysis of the content of the novel *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized* by Marah Rusli based on the literary sociology approach succeeded in identifying the representation of obedience attitudes contained in the story, which can be used as an example in learning Indonesian in elementary schools. The attitude of obedience reflected in the characters of this novel, such as obedience to parents and social norms, is very relevant to the value of character education applied in elementary schools. These values support the formation of the character of students who are disciplined, responsible, and have high social awareness. The implication of these findings is that literature-based character education can increase students' understanding of the importance of obedience in daily life, both in the school environment and in the community. Therefore, it is recommended that teachers use literary works, such as *Sitti Nurbaya: A Love Unrealized*, in learning Indonesian to introduce the values of character education in a more contextual and touching students' feelings. In addition, further research can be conducted to explore the representation of obedience attitudes in other literary works as an additional reference in character education in primary schools.

Confession

Thank you to the Master of Indonesian Education Postgraduate Program at Veteran Bangun Nusantara University.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest.

Reference

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